

**Archetype, the silent protector: good guy in relationship dynamics:
Understanding social media behavior.**

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Abstract:

This review research article explores the complex dynamics of relationships, focusing on the figure of the silent protector, in various relationship stages. I will delve into their social media behaviors, their interaction with the 'one', their stance against dark triads, and their protective nature. This review also aims to offer a comprehensive understanding of the silent protector role in comparison with the 'narcissistic savior' archetype, also, in comparison with the truthful guy archetype, and the angelic guy archetype. A nice guy has typical behavior other than a narcissistic or psychopathic dark triad. The protector's inherent sense of responsibility and commitment sets them apart from these destructive traits. They will have to learn to be truthful as well as nurturing, which will create the angelic guy archetype. Maybe including lessons of empathy and understanding about the pain, trauma, and lack in providing survival chances it caused being half a guy, to true loved ones, which might even motivate them to become a truthful guy as well and make themselves a more complete being. The good guy is a real Superman behaving from love. A protector/ good guy/ nice guy is caused by oxytocin in men making them sweeter. This type is the same as the mother archetype. Archetypes are also evolutionary and inherited, this causes the collective unconscious awareness of the types, and it is instinctively known. Women seek nice guys for long-term relationships. The protector/ good guy/ nice guy/ mother archetype can end up being trauma-bonded by Dark Triads. Dark triads would have the genes mainly from their fathers and the good guys are the mother type, this could also cause an archetype couple, with typical types of children. The abusers work on losing independence, self-esteem, and dignity, which will keep the victim trapped. It is used to have power and control over the good guy, children, one of the good guys, and the loved ones they have. So, they will need to be independent again, build self-esteem, and learn to believe they have dignity. They will also need an escape plan to escape the Dark Triad. Future research, can be about how the protector evolves in changing

environments, with changing societal norms and changing digital landscapes. Also, further research can be about how culture shock can influence this entire process of leaving the Dark Triad, and committing truthfully, besides being a good guy. Further research can explore the marital fraud the Dark Triad actually has within these marriages, and what they used it for, for what crimes.

Keywords: silent, protector, angelic, good guy, nice guy, mother, archetype, oxytocin, online, relationships, social media, dark triad, machiavellism, narcissism, psychopathy, Superman.

The Essence

The silent protector, good guy, and nice guy, are the mother archetype, which has higher oxytocin levels as a cause, and demonstrates responsibility and commitment, setting them apart from darker, more destructive archetypes such as the 'narcissistic savior. Dark Triads mainly get their genes from their fathers, together it creates an archetype couple, with perhaps typical children. Examining the evolution of these archetypes, from the silent protector learning to embody truthfulness and nurturing qualities, thus becoming the 'angelic guy' archetype, to the potential for them to ultimately become a 'truthful guy' archetype. This evolutionary path is seen as a journey towards becoming a more complete being. The article also explores the role of biological factors, such as the influence of oxytocin in men, in shaping these archetypes, and the idea of archetypes as both evolutionary and inherited, contributing to a collective unconscious awareness of these types. Moreover, delves into the dynamics between these archetypes and the 'dark triads,' detailing the potential for trauma bonding, power dynamics, and control tactics used by the latter to maintain dominance over the former. The article concludes with suggestions for future research, including how the 'silent protector' archetype evolves with changing societal norms and digital landscapes, the impact of culture shock on leaving a 'dark triad,' and an investigation into marital fraud within these relationships. In summary, the research seeks to deepen our understanding of relationship dynamics, the evolution and influence of relationship archetypes, and the interplay between these archetypes and more destructive personality types.

Introduction

A nice guy has typical behavior other than a narcissistic or psychopathic dark triad that manipulates, and plays Superman while they set up the scene. The dark triad is no real Superman but a play, an act, a mask, a not real loving, carrying, it is shallow, lacking empathy, has a disregard for rules, and norms, but in a sense like manipulative, and using

people for personal benefits, it is not love, not seeking the real love, not the romantic truthful ethical correct person, and is going into bad situations, and creating bad situations.

The protector's inherent sense of responsibility and commitment sets them apart from these destructive traits. But, only with genuine "true" free will, and when our actions reflect our genuine desires and motivations, we can be held accountable, as the Frankfurt example explains (Ambrosino, 2015; Braham, and van Hees, 2012). Also, but only if committed to the correct things, one is correct (Calhoun, 2009). So, the protector can be responsible or committed, it is a mature type, but it is to wonder what they are committed and feeling responsible for. They will nurture, but what and whom will they nurture? "Commitment is a species of intentions" (Calhoun, 2009, p.615). Also, maybe some commitments and responsibilities are active in them, but perhaps not all commitments, and responsibilities. It binds the future self into these ideas they have today, which one will see especially in a long-term commitment. While the situation is changing, one lives a better or worse situation like married people can, if they stay committed and do not use their free will to be genuine in their actions. This can become a not accountable situation where one is not reflecting genuine desires and motivations, and the marriage can become a dangerous and bad place where one is simply "committed" like criminals can be at a crime scene. Their future is shaped to end up jailed, together with the lie "for better or worse", that initially meant we go be only good together, and then through better or worse, which can become criminal actions and not fitting the true self and true desire of the soul, which came from a younger version of the self, with genuine ideas, and a God's plans. If the intention which it initially had, or the good guy should initially have as truth is another plan, so it had to be committed to that only, to be a real Superman, what is then the good guy over time? Loyal to bad things. Is it then a bad Superman we need to teach the truth? Is it a changed man? Did the origin change? Did it never yet know itself? Why would it become not the original idea of self? This can be further

researched, as this will explain what a real good guy is, how to keep them good, and perhaps teach them some lessons, to remain good and authentic true to self, to be a better man.

If they are aware of the manipulation techniques employed by dark triads and strive to shield their loved ones from such influences, is this a lesson or natural intuition? Can they spot that behavior by contrasting it with themselves? But over time if they changed into worse "selves" this recognition of, them changed into not so capable anymore of seeing right from wrong.

So, they are unlike the 'narcissistic savior' who creates situations to portray themselves as a hero, the silent protector acts authentically. The protector's/ good guy's/ nice guy's actions are driven by genuine concern and love, not a desire for praise or control. They save not by grand gestures, but by providing consistent support, understanding, and guidance. But over time they might lose the idea of who and what to protect, and become a nurturer of bad. This should be further researched, to narrow down to more truth, which can create a more sure idea of the good guy, and help change to a stable being of a good guy, or help to become not only a good guy but also a truthful guy, which would cause a transformation from good guy to angelic guy, if one sees an angelic guy as both good and truthful. Then, we can use the archetypes of the protector/ good guy/ nice guy and also the mother, as a part, perhaps an immature part of the angelic guy or angelic mother. That has lessons to learn to be truthful, and lessons to become complete with also being the archetype of truthful guy or truthful mother. Maybe including lessons of empathy and understanding about the pain, trauma, and lack in providing survival chances it caused being half a guy, to true loved ones, which might even motivate them to become a truthful guy as well and make themselves a more complete being.

A real Superman

Narcissistic and Machiavellism like Jar Jar Binks, who has all three parts of the dark triad, the machiavellistic narcissistic psychopaths, like Joffrey Baratheon from Games of Thrones (Neuro Transmissions, 2016), who is a classic sadistic psychopath, with homicidal plans and fetishes. This would mean that they have a feeling of being similar to him (The Psych Liverpool team, 2018). They also like Superman, who is a good guy they'd love to play with as Dark Triads using Superman for his superpowers, to use his powers as their own. They also love to ruin good people, and cause damage. The dream could be "If you can stop Superman you have a crime-winning". Also, Superman gets attention and is famous, they love fame and attention as well (Neuro Transmission, 2016).

The protector, nice guy, or good guy is a real Superman, and not a borderline-like savior where there is instability, impulsivity, and interpersonal dysfunction, in need of oxytocin, neuropeptides, vasopressin, and opioids to function (Stanley, and Siver, 2010). Love is not about saving it is about love. You could be bad at saving someone, and still be a good guy, or a protector, it is a type of person.

The good guy is a real Superman behaving from love if they find their own personal powers, accidentally, with luck, or if they have a talent for it, they can save someone. They will be empathic and want the best outcomes. What they do is from real love. When they protect and save it is from real love. It is a lucky talent for saving, but it is real and not set up or faked, or with behaviors like using people, or with disregard for rules and ethics.

Oxytocin is biologically causing to be a protector

A protector/ good guy/ nice guy is caused by oxytocin in men making them sweeter.

This type is the same as the mother archetype, also proven by she can have oxytocin as well in her at higher levels, which helps her bond with the baby. It will influence the good bond or bad bond with the baby.

A good guy is a man who is when they are an anima, animus, mentor, shadow, hero's departure, hero's initiation, and hero's return (Chang et al., 2013) like a good mother (Hiraoka et al., 2020), it is a good father. Thus totally as being, from the more animal-like being within them to the shadow they can be, also, when being a mentor and hero, it will be a mother type.

Oxytocin is the reason why an archetype like the protector would develop. Naturally, it causes a different behavior and gives a different social interaction. Stress-relieving, health-promoting, restorative, and restorative effects of nature could activate the oxytocinergic system as well (Grahn, Ottosson, and Uvnäs-Moberg, 2021). So, one could be naturally the good guy, but we could also create an environment creating more good guys.

For example, because of the oxytocin, the behavior of the good guy can cause, a better environment causing oxytocin in the person with borderline, which is then the effect of the good guy on people with borderline behavior that gives them more oxytocin which would help with cortical processing. People with borderline have cortical and limbic problems, which need for the cortical circuit, opioids, vasopressin, and oxytocin, and for the limbic circuit, neuropeptide Y, and neurokinin 1 (Stanley, and Siver, 2010, p.3).

Cortical processing refers to the information processing that occurs in the cerebral cortex, which is the outer layer of the brain responsible for higher cognitive functions. The cortex is divided into different regions.

In the Cortical are the orbitofrontal cortex (OFC) and cingulate cortex. The orbitofrontal cortex (OFC) is located in the frontal lobes of the brain, just above the eyes. It plays a crucial role in processing emotions, decision-making, and reward-related behaviors. The OFC receives input from various sensory systems, such as vision, taste, and smell, as well as from other brain regions involved in emotion regulation. It integrates this information to generate appropriate emotional and behavioral responses. Dysfunction in the orbitofrontal cortex can lead to difficulties in emotional regulation, impaired decision-making, and altered

social behavior. The cingulate cortex is a part of the cerebral cortex that lies in the medial (middle) part of the brain. It is involved in various cognitive processes, including attention, emotion, and motivation. The cingulate cortex is divided into different subregions, with the anterior cingulate cortex (ACC) and the posterior cingulate cortex (PCC) being the most studied.

There might be also an influence on people with ADHD and OCD, as the cingulate cortex is also the anterior Cingulate Cortex (ACC), and the posterior cingulate cortex, also regulates that. The ACC is involved in cognitive control, error detection, conflict monitoring, and decision-making. It plays a role in regulating attention and adapting behavior based on feedback. Dysfunction in the ACC has been associated with disorders such as attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) and obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD). The PCC is involved in various functions, including memory, self-reflection, and spatial orientation. It is part of the default mode network, a network of brain regions that are active when a person is not engaged in specific tasks. The PCC is also implicated in Alzheimer's disease and other neurodegenerative disorders.

The good guy would be involved in processing emotions, decision-making, and reward-related behaviors, but also in, attention, emotion, cognitive control, memory, and self-reflection (Schneider et al. 2020; Stanley, and Siver, 2010).

Stressful situations can lead to bonding and release of neuropeptide oxytocin. Love is about the feeling one is needed and bonding truly like parent and child, with a real need, and not using people. Love is deeply biological, and has healing power (Carter, and Porges, 2012).

People with BPD without medication will respond faster to people with angry faces, and healthy people will respond faster to happy faces. People with an oxytocin state, have the “congruency effect”, this happens in people with BPD as well as in healthy people. When

they have oxytocin they avoid angry faces and go faster to happy faces (Schneider et al., 2020). The environment and influences to create oxytocin within people would then also cause this effect. A real Superman could cause this effect in people with BPD.

The protector is an evolutionary and inherited type

Archetypes are also evolutionary and inherited, this causes the collective unconscious awareness of the types, and it is instinctively known. Archetypes are an ethogram in the studies on behaviors animals have. It is code biology, where sequences in DNA can be understood as related to certain behaviors. One can study reality and existence with it, in realism, focusing on cells and biological systems that exist independently from human interpretation, idealism, or using the human mind and consciousness and how psychological factors influence the performance of reality, constructivism, investigating how scientific concepts are influenced by cultural, historical and societal factors, materialism, where one studies underlying biological systems, dualism, studies about physical and mental aspects of biological systems, perhaps studies about the mind and biological processes, or other philosophies. Then, using the ontological studies in code biology, using DNA and other biological codes. So, it is not metaphorical, it is with organic information and meaning (Major, 2021).

The MBTI types and the protector archetype online in dating and online on social media

The protector can be silent and is a good guy who might be quiet with strength, is loyal, and has a strong sense of responsibility. Despite their considerable presence on social media, they may not actively engage in following or interacting with their significant others on these platforms. For example, an ISFJ protector can be quiet, which is 9-14% of the population as that many people are an ISFJ type, thus silent or quiet protector types (Cherry, 2023).

But the good guy is a protector type and can be also for example, an INFJ, ENFJ, INFP, INTP, ENFP, or ENTP as well, which are all types that can be very quiet. They are introverted, or extroverted feeling and thinking when perceiving or judging, but they are all more quiet. All, types that are introverted can be silent because they draw energy from being in their own feelings or thoughts before expressing them. People that are thoughtful, and reflecting, can be quieter and think or feel about and think through ideas before speaking. Some can prefer listening, instead of talking. Some people can be shy, or have social anxiety.

A loud good guy, and protector, would be an ESTP, ESFP which is more outgoing and expressive, and very vocal about thoughts and opinions.

Introverted, Intuitive and especially Feeling and Perceiving people are online on social media, but this type would be Judging, although a little less than the ones who Perceive. The internet seems for INFP and INFJs, then next the INTP and INTJ, so the same types that are thinkers. Also, ENFPs are online, but they are especially more than others on Facebook. The Extravert, Sensing people are the least online (Yang, et al., 2022). They are not so well at reading between the lines, or being intuitive, perhaps not so well in understanding, or wanting long-distance communication, or non-verbal communication, or in other communication styles, like in texts, etc, it is a difference in communication. While an Intuitive loves introverted or extroverted communication at a distance to see more and feel more than just someone nearby, the experience is different and more about thoughts, being thoughtful, empathic, having feelings, deeply, and also meeting more people, and being more social like an INFJ would, or an ENFP, and ENFJ, they love to express thoughts and feelings. Depth, finding the one, being with more people, or being able to be thoughtful, or empathic is among these very important, also a spiritual, or deeper connection they seek, also more intellectual, or more social. It is for all these types of being in more meaningful relationships and online is the world. The chances to meet the one are bigger too as all people have internet so they will

be online. They do not seek just someone nearby, like random. They seek more meaningful connections. They can also use more ways to communicate and have time to think about it privately. Also, it lets the one perceiving the messages think before they act and be busy with the information they gave in their own personal unique ways. It is not only talking, senses, being together, which will be someone from nearby, which people using senses would seek as else they'd be online. So also sexually they might experience love differently, perhaps rather with some nearby person and love using senses than far away love and deeper connection, with a lot more communication types and more non-verbal, or in texts, and in more expressive ways, like emojis, and thoughtful content.

The silent protector that is online might not be the ISFJ and other IS protectors, but they can be more likely be an INF, INT, ENF, and ENT. Thus, the type of silent protector that seeks the one, the most meaningful relationship, the most thoughtful and expressive in more ways, and non-verbal and creating content to express love. They can be introverted or extroverted in feelings and thoughts. Most likely they have ideas and are very empathic. They might like to practice their words or think about how they will say and express emotions and feelings. This type is not acting from trauma bonding and as a savior per se, like narcissists would, creating the scene and playing Superman. The silent protector, who is the good guy, will be a real Superman but will have different behaviors than if one expects a trauma bonding, and "setting the scene" a Superman.

The sweetness of the oxytocin will cause a different behavior. One will need to learn the typical behavior a good guy has, to understand the behavior they have online. So you can spot them and find the real perfect one to marry, instead of some shocking usage by Dark Triad playing the good guy.

Social media behavior

One might wonder why a silent protector, despite having a big social media account, does not follow their partner. This behavior can be attributed to their respect for their partner's privacy, their desire to prevent any undue influence on their partner's online behavior, and their understanding of the potential toxicity of social media dynamics. They prefer direct, personal interactions to understand and connect with their partners better, rather than relying on the digital representation of their lives. They could keep someone out of their following list, and have them privately somewhere else in some other online place. Especially if they know there will be people around that aren't the best for their true love, and or their children, to get involved with.

To find the community in networks, one can use node-centric, group-centric, network-centric, or hierarchy-centric approaches (Tang, and Liu, 2010). All social media is a kind of community, in total, and someone's channel can be a community as well. Not all types share all their personal or relationship information with communities, and some do. The IS ES types are least online, so a sense of community they might feel less online. IN especially is online, even more, the INXP, but also other INs are online, and the ENXP are most often online. These XNXPs can hide their relationships online or can be indecisive about sharing. The INFP likes space, and the ENFP likes to keep things positive, but INTP likes to give someone their own space, and ENTPs stretch their own limits, and the limits of others. So, their reasons can be different. Some to protect someone, others of these types for privacy or pushing someone's limits. An ENFJ might showcase their relationship, to feel socially accepted. If that is a good guy it will change the idea of how truthful is the good guy as ENFJ showing the real self and real true love. If they show simply whoever they have it has less of a meaning. An INFP seeks the one and will have a more meaningful relationship to show if they show and if they found the one. Then, personal experiences, cultural factors, and

individual circumstances influence the decisions of hiding or showing the relationships. Some might feel the danger of showing a relationship online to others, like an INFJ may fear the judgments of others. But also XXXJ types in general might fear judgements. Fear of social judgment can lead to not showing who someone is with (Moodie, 2017; Moodie 2017b).

The INFJ feels a sense of community but also likes privacy, while the ENFJ feels the need to be a valued member of the community. The INFP wants to be connected to others, but it doesn't have to be in a community. ENFPs want to be liked but don't need to be valued community members. INTJ cares about the community but doesn't feel obligated to do it. ENTJ wants to be valued in the community, but it doesn't want that for the sake of others. INTP cares about freedom and not the community. ENTPs like freedom too and want to be connected but will not want to be valued as a member or avoid that (Moodie, 2017). The IS and ES types are not much online, so they will not use the internet as much to be a part of the community or to be online at all.

When someone is sharing information about their relationship, the intention should fit with the interpretation of the message. So, if it is a real satisfaction, a real positive outcome, and interpreted correctly it will make the partners feel more satisfied in the relationship. Then if the partner they have this satisfaction with is in the profile picture and mentioned in the relationship status they get satisfied, and more intimacy from showing the partner online. If partners disagree on how to show the relationship status online, especially the female partner is dissatisfied. The negative emotions can lead to infidelity and breakups, and lower intimacy and satisfaction. The audience is varied online, so friends, strangers, and the romantic partner will see it, but also other people, that might normally would not see it if it was offline. The self-presentation, and expression of the relationship information, and the relationship with others come together online, and constantly. It will not go away, they are always around. The depth of sharing information would be more important than the width, from side to side of the

information that could be shared. Intimacy would fit the beginning of the relationship, satisfaction fits the length of the relationship. Love online, is two things, being online and being romantic. The more one shares online about the relationship, the less intimate and satisfied one is, and the more offline one shares about the relationship the more intimate and satisfied one is. So, seeking attention won't work, because one is not honest, and it's not truly the intention there is in love, It is not matching the feelings and interpretation of the truth within, but also it is oversharing thus the least intimacy. The dark triad will never be satisfied. They will want an overshare, and a lie, so they get double dissatisfaction.

Friends though will not have any effect from being online and exposing information about the relationship there. They do have more intimacy and satisfaction if one shows offline more information about their relationship, but if it is done online it has no effect. There is only one effect on romantic relationships. So, perhaps if one were friends online and become a romantic relationship, there are sudden effects from being online as well as couples and sharing information about the relationship online (Lee et al., 2019).

The good guy will be honest, will get the real interpretation, and will be deep, and not overshare. They think of ethics, and rules, are empathic and will think of the partner, decide to share or not share some things, and will protect the partner from oversharing. They will find a balance, of sharing, meeting the desires, and interpreting them correctly, but also will be online and offline in the relationship with the one they truly love, and will not only have an online relationship or only an offline relationship. Especially the online types who are introverted, expressing their thoughts, feelings, and ideas as the content they will share, but at the same time are empathic, deep, interpret well, and will be satisfied in the relationship, as well as online as offline. The good guy will try to meet offline as well. He will tell more offline, than online (Braham, and van Hees, 2012; Chang et al., 2013; Hiraoka et al., 2020; Lee et al., 2019; Grahn, Ottosson, and Uvnäs-Moberg, 2021).

The good guy might suddenly stop sharing information about the romantic relationship they have, and hide her. He also might stop talking online and seek an offline relationship. As it is an honest serious deep person, especially met online it is most likely the introverted intuitive expressing feelings and thoughts in ideas and content, he will seek to express this also in person. The female especially will need to see herself back in the profile picture but will not get satisfaction from a lot of sharing online about the relationship. She will need an offline relationship as well, but perhaps the good guy leads her to that, while she doesn't know what she wants, yet. He might show her like Superman. With the superpower of "he is not seeking this online sharing of information" about his relationship as much. The dark triad does. The good guy though might feel pressured to show someone and will not disclose the real one to protect her and to build a real deep romantic relationship, including meeting her offline, where he will express suddenly a lot more to her. She might be surprised as she is more focused on being in the profile picture and he withdraws from being online, while it is a type to be online. He will tell her like Clark Kent, suddenly, offline, he is Superman.

On the other side, he can be loyal to the wrong people (Calhoun, 2009), also, Dark Triads want to use the good guy's fame, attention, and superpowers (Neuro Transmission, 2016), especially when trauma bonded and forced, their will is not free, they are drained and used and will not be showing the real motivations (Braham, and van Hees, 2012). The decision to follow the abusive wife or family instead of letting the one be in the same list, or have instead only the true one on the list, could be due to various reasons such as maintaining appearances for the sake of the children, or to avoid fueling further conflict. It does not reflect his feelings toward the 'one'. Initially, he only will, if the situation is safe and he feels comfortable, he might openly follow and interact with the 'one' on social media. However, if he perceives any risk or potential harm, he could choose to unfollow to avoid drawing attention or causing misunderstandings. His actions would be dictated by his protective

instincts and the desire to maintain the 'one's safety and privacy. If he feels the need to unfollow the 'one', it would likely stem from his intention to protect her from any potential backlash or harm, especially if he is still in the process of extricating himself from the abusive relationship. He would consider refollowing when the situation is stable and safe, and when he feels ready to publicly acknowledge their relationship. This decision would be based on his assessment of the situation and the potential impact on the 'one' and their relationship. If he chooses not to follow the 'one' on social media, he will find other ways to express his love and commitment. This could include direct communication, thoughtful gestures, and spending quality time together. His actions would speak louder than his social media activity. He could have a journey of finding out who he really is, what he wants to share in the communities, and how to protect his real love and children. He also will need to have an escape plan, to escape the Dark Triads.

The Silent Protector and The 'One'

In the context of dating, love, twin souls, and marriage stages, the silent protector is often more nurturing, patient, understanding, and devoted, this causes more resilience in the one, as it does to the babies of a great mother (Alvares Biscaro, 2022). They are not likely to have multiple partners, as their focus tends to be on deep, meaningful connections rather than shallow relationships, but also they bond deeper because of the oxytocin levels being higher within them, which makes them "the good guy". Which can come from a better environment causing higher oxytocin, or from genetics, but also from "the one" in the ways the good guy senses the one, and can pick up on the stability of the relationship they have with them, or could have with them, or should have with them. This will have to be when he makes an initiation to contact her to raise her oxytocin levels, and she has to want sex to cause a rise in the oxytocin levels in him, which causes a monogamous relationship (Snowdown et al., 2010). They may take their time in finding 'the one', but once they do, they are committed

and steadfast in their support and protection. But it will depend on how well they can commit to truth and are also truthful guys to be actually with the twin flame, soulmate, or one. Especially if it is an ENFJ, or lost IN or EN, or hiding the true one as xxxJ, fearing judgments of others. This behavior extends to their parenting stage, as they are the mother archetype, where they provide a safe and loving environment for their children while teaching them the importance of respect and independence, but will they teach about the true one? About staying truthful and seeking the twin soul, or soulmate? It will depend on the type and on if the good guy is also a truthful guy, thus more of an angelic archetype. Also, if he is lost, or not himself, it will depend on how he finds himself back or finds his truth, and eventually meets the one. The lessons on truth will matter a lot, as on the twin souls, and Dark Triad, and other lessons helping them to be their true selves, find the true one, believe, and recognize the preying Dark Triad, and choose the self instead, where the one is attached to, as the real one is the real gender, how one is born, not just someone, or a person in society one is with because of societal pressure. Also, steps out of trauma bonding, dark triad abuse, and steps towards the one, like dating, love, and marriage stages. It all depends on the truth to have the real one, and also, on knowing all variables that are important in being authentic, finding truth, and everything about love relationships, and relationships in general to narrow down to the real one and best relationships.

Women seek nice guys for long-term relationships and physically attractive men for casual sex (Urbaniak and Kilman, 2003). Women can think nice guys have fewer sexual relationships. Good guys are more desired by others to be in a committed relationship with. So, they will have a lot of people wanting them, wanting to marry them. They will be very popular, loved by the people, and very wanted. Women who actually seek a good guy will have fewer sexual relationships, find sex not important, and will not accept men who do have a lot of sexual partners (Herold and Milhausen. 1999). The good guy perhaps has it even

harder to find the one as he is a popular person, but is also preyed on by Dark Triads. Also, online everyone sees and all types of relationships come together. Maybe he finds her online best, but will take her offline, and will always show his love, but in more ways, because it is most likely an IN EN and online, they have other ways to express and communicate but also can be introverted and not express the same as others would, and can be expressing online in different communication types as it is also a different communication online than offline.

Dark Triad uses good guys

The protector/ good guy/ nice guy/ mother archetype can end up being trauma bonded by Dark Triads, as they are nice and such criminal type loves empathic people, and love to manipulate and target them to use and abuse them, also, with simply sadistic or morbid ideas. It is a play to them, also to ruin them. The Dark Triad will play a Superman vs. this real Superman and might even target them to simply target good people, and use them for their own benefits, by trauma bonding them they can use the superpowers of the real Superman (Frazier, Ferreira, and Gonzales, 2019).

1 in 33 men was raped in 2004, this could have increased or decreased in the past 20 years, it would need further research to know the changes, but also, the effectiveness of prevention. A part of the prevention should be understanding the dark triad seeks the good guy to exploit, enforce marriage, and make kids, as it serves the dark triad. This comes along with a lot of trauma bonding, manipulations, setting scenes, and actual marriage fraud, thus deceiving, and creating a different situation than one actually marries into. Also, it can be part of war plans to target countries and their good men, to ruin them, and also, crime scenes in general target specific people. The effect of prevention was just 14% in 2004. 80% fail (Morrison et al., 2004). So, we will need further research to understand what prevention should be precisely and make it effective and cause no more marriages between dark triad and good guys. Also, no more usage of courts, and enslaving men in marriages that seem

legal, or seem free will, but actually it is simply getting some paperwork done, to further abuse the man. Also, to forever further exploit the men and their kids, after divorce. Also, some women kill the men and their family members, or children, or cause "miscarriages", everything seems to be not illegal when it is done in the home, during certain weeks of pregnancy, etc. We will need to see every detail and understand every part and find these types of women and save the men really, without court cases needed where one hardly can prove what happened.

We do need to study further on the fact the nice guy is the prey of psychopaths and other dark triads, that will force sex from them. If a nice guy is very popular, the chances of more sexual partners, or more forced sex might increase, despite they would originally keep that number of sex partners down. So, perhaps another type would end up with even more partners, but it is to further research how this functions in the good guy. So, one sees if being raped, or having more sexual partners but would originally only do the one, or one person, why this is still happening the Dark Triad loves to change the look of the Supermen, so they seem bad, as well. We will need to know all the details everything about the manipulation and twists the Dark Triad creates.

We should look at the motives and other behaviors to determine if he is a nice guy, what has happened, and if they saved others and themselves, as well, from the Dark Triad. That talent to save others and themselves they can lack as much as the good women who got trapped by Dark Triads, which could increase the outside look of having more sexual partners as well, which causes a different and wrong treatment and no real help truly to them. They might even lie for it, to survive, and pretend to be fine with the forced sex. So, we will need to look through those things and find the real truth within the person.

Dark triads would have the genes mainly from their fathers (Frazier et al., 2019, p.5), and the good guys are the mother type. So, they both could be the archetypes of the bad father

and the good mother, as well. Or the bad and the good father. We could further research how these are together. Maybe there is even a connection, between the good mother, and the bad father, or over time in past generations a typical passing on of genes. The Dark Triad MOA gene is also related to ADHD (Frazier, et al., 2019, p.5.1), although they are different criminals in a crime spectrum, compared to the Dark Triad, it might explain some behaviors. Also, serotonin and the 5-HTT gene are related to aggression and Dark Triad behavior, where the short allele is not related to aggression and the long allele of the 5-HTT is, where socioeconomic changes can trigger these behaviors. In both MOA and 5-HTT trauma is not related, it is more a genetic situation why someone is a Dark Triad. As sweet genes can also be inherited and Oxytocin might be caused also genetically, we might need also the relationship in the children if they carry all these genes, mixed together. Then, we can also see the archetype of the family with a Dark Triad father, and Sweet Gened mother, with their typical children, that perhaps also are archetypes coming out of this. Perhaps causing certain sibling behaviors, like some good guys, that can be too loyal to psychopathic killing siblings. Or psychopathic siblings, killing the entire family, eventually. Fratricidal serial killers can be driven by a need for dominance over their siblings, wanting to look like an authority in the family, and using violence to maintain control and power over their siblings. Fratricidal means brother, sorroris, mean sister. So, if a killer is motivated by intense jealousy or envy towards their sisters, one will be referring to sorroris, which means sister, they kill. They want to eliminate their success and happiness. This can also be collaborative fratricidal serial killers, including friends, or mobs work together to commit serial sibling killings, with a shared responsibility, and coordination involved. Group-assisted Sibling serial killers can be done with friends or mobs as well, relying on the support, planning, and execution provided by the group. Or coordinated fratricidal syndicate, which is also with friends or a mob, but it's

about the hierarchy in the group. Especially if they have a distant ideology (Gade et al., 2019).

There could be numerous reasons why the silent protector got trapped in an abusive relationship, being preyed on, or reasons such as manipulation, societal or family pressure, or fear for their children's well-being. It's not necessarily typical for a 'good guy' to get trapped in such situations, but it's not uncommon either, considering the manipulative tactics often used by abusive individuals.

Escape plan for the good guy

Because the good guy is a mother type, they will despite being in an abusive situation, continue to uphold values of protection and care. Their primary concern would be the well-being of their children, trying to shield them from the harmful effects of the abusive environment. They might limit their social media interactions to avoid fueling any further abuse or misunderstandings. Or not follow the one, and follow the abuser online in their social media. Or other behaviors influenced by the situation.

Leaving an abusive relationship is a complicated process, especially as a hidden victim, which men are often (Hine et al., 2022), and requires careful planning. First, it would have to be acknowledged they are abused, and they might be hidden victims, but there can be screening done. Then, they will decide to leave, but at the same time, there must be thought about the children and safety concerns. Did abuse increase? Did she use or threaten to use weapons? Does he believe she can kill him? Was he beaten in vulnerable times, or since he is a father? Is she violently and constantly jealous of him? Then, he will need to have safety behaviors. Know where he and the children can hide, and have a list of contacts ready, that can help. Also, for professional help. He will need to memorize the numbers. He will need to have change with him, all the time. During this time, they might subtly hint to the 'one' about their circumstances, without directly involving them in the situation. He will need to create

signs or code words for the one and everyone who can help, but also with the children. Code words should also be made with the children to know to leave immediately the home, or to call for help. He will need to think about what he will say if she gets violent.

Once they have successfully exited the abusive situation, he would need time to heal and regain their emotional stability. But he will need to think of changing locks, and numbers, and not be alone. Also, have information and important documents ready about her and what she did. If he has to meet her it must be in public places. He has to vary his routine he will need to contact the school and work contacts. He will need to have shelter places ready (Choo, and Houry, 2015). They would then gradually start communicating more openly with the 'one', expressing their feelings and intentions. However, they might still refrain from following or interacting with the 'one' on social media until they feel ready to publicly acknowledge their relationship. It will depend on the safety. The issue is he can't take time, the kids need protection, but the one too. She depends on him too. This needs further research. We cannot pretend she won't have a life at stake as well, she does, so it is about saving all. Him trapped, doesn't mean his one, isn't now missing her life and safety. She is. It can even be the reason why the criminal targeted him, so his one has no one and is targeted as well, at the same time, and the kids too, so all are targeted. They cannot contact, as the good guy will not think of it, or not know how. He will not know, but she could be dead already. He will need to learn to do truth and care more, deeper, and compete, during the targeting and bad times. He will need to see it as a professional job, where all can be attacked. We will need to teach people the complete story. People need to learn to be truthful, and good, which is the angelic archetype, but also people need to be complete and professional. It is traumatic for each and for all like after narc and psychopathic abuse, learning to speak again. So, they also cannot speak well anymore, since such women caught them and used them. Who is also attacking his family and others, and this can be done with siblings or some family members

or relatives of the family., or with mobs. They will use third parties to do their crimes. Where they hope to use him and make him look online and offline taken, and in love with someone else and a part of the killers, or other crime groups. He might not pay attention to normal living anymore, together with the one. She is delayed, has a lacking situation, and hurtful situation, but also her kids, and loved ones. So, the one did not get a normal life, not a birthday, or her birthday and other special days were always ruined by the Dark Triads that targeted them.

The 'one' can play a supportive role during this time, offering emotional support and understanding. However, it is crucial that they give the silent protector the space and time to heal and make decisions at their own pace. Direct intervention in the abusive situation should be avoided unless he explicitly asks for help.

If the process takes many years, it's crucial to maintain hope and patience. The silent protector would need to focus on their mental health and well-being, as well as that of their children. Regular therapy or counseling can be beneficial during this time.

Despite the challenging circumstances, the silent protector would continue to protect those they care about, including the 'one' and their children.

How to "un-brainwash" the good guy

The abusers work on losing independence, self-esteem, and dignity, which will keep the victim trapped. It is used to have power and control over the good guy, children, one of the good guys, and the loved ones they have. So, they will need to be independent again, build self-esteem, and learn to believe they have dignity.

The brainwashes are similar to war, hostages, and members of cults. They isolate, humiliate, accuse, and have unpredictable attacks. They create real and anticipated fear, to make them believe the situation is hopeless, and that they depend on the abuser, or abusers, as

they also use mobs, and other criminals. So, they will need to be freed, and process the emotions and fears.

They will develop coping strategies but will feel fatigued like in wars, and battles living in fear of being killed. We need to recognize the state of mind they have, so they will not kill themselves (Britannica, T. Editors of Encyclopaedia, 2023; Mega et al., 2000). Mobs were used by the mafias and Sovjet war in the Cold War and in religious wars, cults, drug wars, gang wars, etc (Kemp et al., 2020).

Fasten the protector to marry the one

To fasten the situation to marriage, it's crucial to remember that healing and building a healthy relationship takes time. Patience and understanding from the 'one' can help create a supportive environment for the silent protector/ good guy/ nice guy. Regular, open communication about their feelings and future plans can also help move the relationship forward. To assist the silent protector, emotional support, patience, and understanding are essential. While the 'one' can offer support, remember that the decision to seek help and leave the abusive relationship must ultimately come from the silent protector himself.

"Getting rid" of an abusive spouse is a delicate process that usually requires legal intervention. He will need to know his options.

One can use the commitment model, with a transformation in motivation, creating common goals can fasten the relationship and make it a committed relationship, creating a couple's identity (Stanley et al., 2010). One needs to learn to be a truthful guy as well and make the combination between a good guy and a truthful guy to be an angelic guy. Being complete, and letting the good guy commit correctly to the correct one and not let him be loyal to the criminals. He must nurture truth.

Future research

Future research, can be about how the protector evolves in changing environments, with changing societal norms and changing digital landscapes. Further exploration could focus on how these individuals navigate their relationships in the face of increasing online interaction and whether their approach changes across different cultures. Also, further research can be about how culture shock can influence this entire process of leaving the Dark Triad, and committing truthfully, besides being a good guy. Further research can explore the marital fraud the Dark Triad actually has within these marriages, and what they used it for, for what crimes. Also, it can help to further research on all possible crimes these women hide in such marriage, and how to find out in detail what it did and with whom, with what mobs, etc.

Practical Implications

The findings of this research article have practical implications for relationship counseling and personal development. Recognizing the silent protector's traits can help individuals and therapists better understand their actions and motivations, leading to healthier relationships. Moreover, understanding the contrast between the silent protector and the 'narcissistic savior' can assist in identifying and avoiding potentially toxic relationships. Helping free the good guy from the Dark Triads, helping save their children, and building a case so men can be the single parents in these cases, giving them guardianship.

Conclusion

The silent protector's actions are driven by his protective nature and his love for the 'one'. Even if his social media activity may seem confusing, his offline actions and direct communication should provide a clearer picture of his feelings and intentions. But also he is a good guy and might not share, and keep the same situation up online and offline. So, you'd have to really know him and understand his behavior, but also really interpret him.

This journey requires strength, patience, and careful planning. The silent protector's inherent resilience and protective nature would guide them through this challenging process, helping them eventually reach a place of safety and happiness with the 'one'.

Navigating social media in the context of complex relationships is a delicate task. The silent protector, given his concern for the well-being and privacy of those he cares about, may approach this in various ways.

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